

Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Cobalt with Substituted Pyridines and Thiocyanate

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Cobalt(II) forms complexes with α -picoline/ β -picoline/ γ -picoline/2 : 4 : 6-collidine in thiocyanate system. These complexes are readily extractable into ethylacetate. All species absorb sharply at 620 nm. The colour of the extracts is extremely stable and can be directly measured spectrophotometrically. The sensitivities are 0.040, 0.040, 0.045, $0.035 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2} \text{Co}^{2+}$ and molar absorptivities are 1.415×10^3 , 1.485×10^3 , 1.375×10^3 and $1.721 \times 10^3 \text{ l mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for α -pic., β -pic., γ -pic. and 2 : 4 : 6-collidine, respectively. A quick and very simple method has been proposed for determination of microgram amounts of cobalt in presence of copper and iron and other metal ions.

THE studies on the extraction and other chemical behaviour of the pyridine thiocyanate complex of cobalt is known in the literature¹⁻³, but the extraction studies with different substituted pyridines in presence of thiocyanate are not reported. Under suitable conditions, cobalt forms pyridine thiocyanate complex readily. The structure for the cobalt complex has been given¹ as $\text{CoPy}_4(\text{SCN})_2$. The conditions under which this compound forms was examined and a procedure was described for the separation of cobalt and nickel as pyridine thiocyanate using solvent extraction by methyl isobutyl ketone⁴. In the present communication, we report the results of our studies on the extraction behaviour of cobalt(II) with α -picoline, β -picoline, γ -picoline and 2 : 4 : 6-collidine in thiocyanate system using ethyl acetate. Based on these studies, a rapid and sensitive method for the extraction and spectrophotometric determination of trace amounts of cobalt(II) has been developed.

Experimental

Absorbance measurements were carried out with a Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer with optically matched quartz cells (1 cm). ECL 5651 digital pH meter was used for pH measurements. Ethyl acetate (E. Merck), α -picoline (Riedel), β -picoline (BDH), γ -picoline (Fluka) and 2 : 4 : 6-collidine (BDH) were distilled before use. Ammonium thiocyanate (BDH) solution (30%, w/v) was prepared in double-distilled water. All other chemicals were either chemically pure or analytical reagent grade. A stock solution of cobalt sulphate was standardized by EDTA using xylenol orange indicator⁵. Solutions of appropriate concentrations were prepared by dilution.

An aliquot containing 100-800 μg of cobalt was transferred to a 50 ml separatory funnel and water

added as necessary to give a total volume of 5 ml. Ammonium thiocyanate (1 ml), dil. HCl (2 ml, $\sim 2N$) and α -pic./ β -pic./ γ -pic./2 : 4 : 6 collidine (1 ml) were added by swirling and finally the volume was made to 10 ml by adding water. 20 ml of ethyl acetate was added and the mixture was equilibrated by shaking for 2 min. After phase separation, lower aqueous phase was drained out and ethyl acetate layer collected in 25 ml volumetric flask and diluted to the mark by excess solvent. The absorbance of the sample solution was measured against a reagent blank at 620 nm. Amount of cobalt extracted was finally computed from a previously prepared calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Absorption curves : The spectral curves of the Co^{2+} picolines thiocyanate complexes in ethyl acetate over the spectral range 550-700 nm are shown in Fig. 1. The reagents absorb quite insignificantly over this spectral range. In each case the distinctive peak at 620 nm was chosen for analytical measurements. The tail of the peak of each complex becomes a shoulder near 580 nm.

Effect of acidity : In each case the percentage of metal ion extracted was studied as a function of pH by varying hydrochloric acid concentration. In α -pic.-SCN and 2 : 4 : 6-collidine-SCN system a broad pH range was found where complete extraction of the metal is possible. In Fig. 2, extent of extraction of cobalt complex as a function of pH is shown by a composite diagram.

Calibration curve : Different amounts of cobalt were extracted, as described in the general procedure, at the corresponding pH and the absorbances were measured. In all the cases reagent blanks were prepared. The aqueous phase after each extraction was clear and colourless. The Beer's

law ranges for the amount of $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ Co^{II} ethyl acetate in α -pic.-SCN, β -pic.-SCN, γ -pic.-SCN, and 2 : 4 : 6-collidine-SCN are 4-40, 4-40, 4.5-45, and 3.5-35, respectively.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectrum of cobalt complex. — 2 : 4 : 6-collidine-SCN, - - - γ -pic.-SCN, - · - β -pic.-SCN, · · · α -pic.-SCN.

Fig. 2. % Extraction of cobalt complex as function of pH. — 2 : 4 : 6-collidine-SCN, - - - α -pic.-SCN, · · · β -pic.-SCN, - · - γ pic.-SCN.

Molar absorptivity and sensitivity : The molar absorptivities of the complexes were calculated at 620 nm and found to be 1.415×10^3 , 1.485×10^3 , 1.375×10^3 and 1.721×10^3 $\text{l mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ for α -pic., β -pic., γ -pic. and 2 : 4 : 6-collidine, respectively. Sensitivities, in terms of Sandell's definition⁶, are

0.040, 0.040, 0.045 and 0.035 $\mu\text{g Co}^{II} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, respectively. In methyl isobutyl ketone, sensitivity⁴ of $\text{Co(Py)}_4(\text{SCN})_2$ is 0.02 $\mu\text{g Co}^{II} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. Thus it may be concluded that for relatively lower cobalt concentration pyridine itself has some advantage over its substituted analogues.

Effect of reagents concentration : Variation of reagent concentration was tested at the corresponding pH keeping the other variables same. It was found that 1 ml of the respective reagents and 1 ml aqueous ammonium thiocyanate (25%, w/v) are sufficient to extract 1000 μg of Co^{II} . Amount of organic reagents below 1 ml and aqueous thiocyanate (25%) below 1 ml resulted in incomplete extraction. Higher concentrations (1 ml for 100% organic reagents and 1 ml for 25% aq. thiocyanate) had no effect on extraction and was avoided because of reagent economy.

Extraction time : The absorbance of Co^{II} picolines-thiocyanate in ethyl acetate was tested as a function of extraction time. The absorbance was essentially constant for the extraction time range 1.5-3 min.

Stability of colour of the extract : The absorbance values of ethyl acetate extract containing 200-1000 $\mu\text{g Co}^{II}$ were measured at different intervals of time. The colour of the complexes in the organic phase was found to be stable even after seven days.

Efficiency of extraction : The extent of extraction was investigated quantitatively by developing the colour of Co^{II} in the aqueous phase after extraction by the recommended procedure. Excess thiocyanate of the aqueous phase was destroyed and cobalt content was determined by 2,2'-pyridyl monooxime method⁷. An average 3 μg of cobalt was detected in the aqueous phase after extraction of three separate solutions containing 500 μg cobalt. Considering the reliability of this method, more than 99.4% of the cobalt is extracted.

Effect of foreign ions : The selectivity of the recommended procedure was investigated by the determination of 20 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of cobalt in the presence of a number of other ions. An ion was considered to interfere if the absorbance obtained differed by more than $\pm 2\%$ from that for cobalt alone. The following metal (M) ions, added as chloride, nitrate or sulphate cause no interference at the Co : M weight ratio given, $\text{Be} \geq 200$, $\text{Mg}^{II} \geq 150$, $\text{Ca}^{II} \geq 100$, $\text{Sr}^{II} \geq 100$, $\text{Ba}^{II} \geq 100$, $\text{Zn}^{II} \geq 100$, $\text{Cd}^{II} \leq 75$, $\text{Hg}^{II} \leq 50$, $\text{La}^{III} \leq 400$, $\text{Al}^{III} \geq 300$, $\text{Ni}^{II} \leq 10$, $\text{Pd}^{II} \leq 5$, $\text{Pt}^{IV} \leq 10$, $\text{Rh}^{III} \leq 20$, $\text{Zr}^{IV} \leq 100$, $\text{U}^{VI} \leq 100$, $\text{Th}^{IV} \geq 100$, $\text{Mn}^{II} \geq 150$, $\text{Fe}^{III} \leq 100$, $\text{Cu}^{II} \leq 8$ and alkali metals ≥ 500 . Among anions, phosphate, acetate, fluoride, tartrate, borate, molybdate, bromide, iodide, thio-sulphate (added as alkali metal salts) do not interfere even when their weight is at least 300 times than that of cobalt. Tolerance limit of oxalate and citrate ions are quite low. Only 1.5 mg oxalate

ion and 2.0 mg citrate ion permit quantitative extraction of $20 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ Co, while trace amount of EDTA prevents cobalt from extracting quantitatively to the organic phase. An excess amount of tartrate ion aptly removes the interference of Fe^{2+} . A sufficiently large excess of thiosulphate ion prevents Cu^{2+} from co-extracting to the organic phase. Tolerance limits of Pd^{2+} , Pt^{4+} , Rh^{3+} and Ni^{2+} could not be improved either by adding excess reagents or by using common masking agents. In the presence of Pd^{2+} , Pt^{4+} and U^{6+} the organic extract turns green. This is probably due to co-extraction of these metals with cobalt to the organic layer. However, in the presence of the amount indicated earlier for these three metal ions cobalt complex offers a steady absorbance value as expected for its own.

Determination of Co^{2+} in synthetic mixtures : Following three mixtures were prepared and cobalt content of each of these mixtures was determined by the recommended procedure.

- Mixture (i) : 0.5 mg Co^{2+} + 50 mg Fe^{3+} + 15 mg Ni^{2+} per 5 ml.
 Mixture (ii) : 0.5 mg Co^{2+} + 15 mg Cu^{2+} + 15 mg Ni^{2+} per 5 ml.
 Mixture (iii) : 0.5 mg Co^{2+} + 50 mg Mn^{2+} + 50 mg Fe^{3+} per 5 ml.

For mixtures (i) and (iii) an excess amount of tartrate ion and for mixture (ii) an excess of thio-sulphate ion was added prior to addition of the reagents. All the three mixtures offered quite satisfactory results with α -pic./ β -pic./ γ -pic., 2 : 4 : 6 collidine, and thiocyanate.

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